

An aerodynamic sensitivity study of large aspect-ratio wings with distributed propulsion for conceptual airframe definition

Marco Fossati*, Bryn Jones†, Peter Nagy‡
University of Strathclyde, Glasgow, G1 1XJ, United Kingdom

Martin Hepperle§
Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt, Braunschweig, Germany

A sensitivity study is presented aiming to explore the impact of different propeller-based distributed propulsion solutions on the aerodynamic performance of a large aspect-ratio wing airframe. The study will develop an aerodynamic surrogate using adaptive high-dimensional model representation and Kriging to: 1) identify the design parameters in the integration of a distributed propulsion system and large aspect-ratio wing configurations that have the largest impact on the aerodynamic characteristics of the wing and 2) quantify the impact of these parameters at a level relevant for the conceptual design of unconventional aircraft configurations integrating these technologies. The analysis will consider large aspect-ratio strut-braced wings with the added interest in assessing the role of the wing strut in the aerodynamic behaviour of such configurations.

I. Introduction

REDUCING the impact that aviation has on climate is one of the top priorities in the agenda of policy makers and the aerospace industry as a means to ensure sustainability of aerospace activities. In a landscape where many evolutionary technologies and solutions are constantly progressed - even if often in isolation - there is the compelling need for a step change enabling for a substantial improvement of aviation environmental impact [1,2]. The integration of aircraft technologies such as Distributed Hybrid Electric Propeller-based propulsion systems (DHEP) and Large Aspect Ratio Wings (LARW, AR > 25) offers several opportunities to achieve the net-zero aviation vision [3-5]. LARW airframes offer better aerodynamic performance during cruise but also have advantages when looking at near airport operations. They allow for shorter take-off, steeper climbs and low-power descent. DHEP is recognised to be capable of substantially reducing emissions at source by exploiting electric / SAF powertrains. It provides additional help in shortening the take-off distance thanks to the efficiency of distributed propellers. In combination with the installation on LARW airframes, DHEP would offer opportunities for introducing advanced noise reduction technologies on top of the inherent advantage of reduced noise levels, yaw control and aeroelastic benefits in relation to propellers being distributed along a large-span wing and offering possibility to exploit more shielding effects.

The installation of distributed propulsion on a large aspect ratio airframe is an important design step that will have impact at different levels, i.e. aerodynamics, aeroacoustics, structural and aeroelastic. A lot of effort has been put forward in the recent years to explore different configurations and solutions of distributed propulsion over large aspect-ratio wings [6-8]. While sufficiently-reliable low-fidelity methods are yet to be developed for this type of configurations, work has been done by means of high-fidelity computational fluid dynamics simulations and wind tunnel experiments. These approaches are very powerful but not always can be employed in the early stages of the design, where system-level decisions on the aircraft concept need to be taken.

This work proposes an approach to develop a system-level understanding of the installation of DHEP on LARW airframe by using adaptive high-dimensional model representation and Kriging-based reduced order modelling. Focusing on the early design stages, e.g. conceptual design, the proposed approach will allow: 1) identifying the hierarchy of design parameters in terms of the ones providing the highest impact on aerodynamic performance such as Lift and

*Professor, Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, 75 Montrose St, Glasgow G1 1XJ, AIAA Member

†Post-doctoral researcher, Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, 75 Montrose St, Glasgow G1 1XJ, AIAA Member

‡PhD Student, Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, 75 Montrose St, Glasgow G1 1XJ, AIAA Student Member

§Senior researcher, Institute of Aerodynamics and Flow Technology, Lilienthalplatz 7, 38108 Braunschweig

2) providing an initial quantification of the changes in Lift characteristics resulting from changes in the design and installation of the DHEP on LARW airframes.

The manuscript is presented in the following format. Section II will introduce the methodology adopted for the parametric study. This will cover the adaptive-cut high dimensional model representation (HDMR) approach and the Vortex Lattice Method (VLM) to allow for fast and accurate evaluations of aerodynamic performance. Section III will introduce the development of a cost-effective surrogate to evaluate Lift characteristics of the LARW-DHEP aircraft. Section IV will present the results of the sensitivity study considering and comparing DHEP solutions with a different number of distributed propellers.

II. A vortex lattice method-based Adaptive High-dimensional Model Representation

The Adaptive-cut High Dimensional Model Representation (A-cut-HDMR) is a probabilistic non-intrusive method that decomposes the general function response, $f(\mathbf{U})$, in a sum of the contributions given by each uncertainty variable and each one of their interactions through the model, considered as increments with respect to the response in the anchor point (not necessarily the nominal response), f_c [9-11]:

$$f(\mathbf{U}) = f_c + \sum_{i=1}^{N_u} F_i(U_i) + \sum_{i < j \leq N_u} F_{i,j}(U_i, U_j) + \dots + F_{1,2,\dots,N_u}(U_1, U_2, \dots, U_{N_u}), \quad (1)$$

where N_u is the number of parameters, $F_i, i = 1, \dots, N_u$, are the orthogonal incremental contributions of every single uncertain parameter, $F_{i,j}, 1 \leq i < j \leq N_u$, are the incremental contributions of each pair of uncertain parameters and $F_{1,2,\dots,N_u}$ is the incremental contribution of the interaction of all the uncertain parameters. A surrogate model representation can be independently generated for each incremental contribution and only for the non-zero elements, thus greatly reducing the complexity of sampling and building the model. Moreover, the contribution of each term of the sum to the global response can be quantified independently so that higher-order interactions with low or zero contribution can be neglected already by analysing the lower-order terms. This approach can be used to propagate any known standard distribution, from the classic Gaussian and uniform to Gumbell and Landau ones, and also non-standard distributions, as those deriving from the sum of kernels. The only assumption is the independence of the input uncertainties.

Not only is the output of this method the distribution of the quantity of interest, but also the quantification of the global contribution of each term of the sum to the global response. This feature allows for a complete analysis of the sensitivity of the response with respect to each of the stochastic variables, as well as their interactions. Moreover, in the case that the output function of interest is given by a black-box model, the analysis of the single contributions can give an insight into the structure of the response function. The surrogate modelling also allows for a histogram of the output to be plotted based on the input uncertainties in a computationally efficient manner. The A-cut-HDMR is adaptive in terms of sampling and truncation of terms in Eq. (1). The adaptive sampling takes into account the shape of the underlying response and also the input probability distributions, leading to an efficient distribution of samples for the considered uncertainties and combination of uncertainties. The adaptive truncation removes the interactions that give a contribution to the overall response lower than a predefined threshold.

The HDMR methodology requires the evaluation of the function response to infer some knowledge about the system under study, In the present work, the function response of interest is the $C_L(\alpha)$ curve for LARW-DHEP. Given that the aim to perform an analysis to inform the conceptual design phase, the standard Vortex Lattice Method [12] has been used to obtain the aerodynamic performance of such aircraft in a cost-effective manner. The VLM is very well-known in the literature. It uses infinitely thin sheet of discrete vortices applied to each panel of the aircraft surface discretisation to obtain a pressure distribution, and thus the aerodynamic force and moments. VLM offers a convenient way to explore the aerodynamic performance of aircraft but in the present study, due to the large number of different geometrical parameters for the LARW and the DHEP an even faster method will be introduced to allow for a very large exploration of the parameter space. The VLM incorporating actuator disk model [13, 14] will be considered as the method offering a reference solution for the $C_L(\alpha)$ curve and its solutions will be used to inform the generation of a Kriging-based surrogate as detailed in Section III.

A. LARW-DHEP concept and set-up of the HDMR sensitivity study

The sensitivity analysis will consider a medium-range large aspect ratio wing aircraft with strut-bracing and a distributed propulsion with one large hybrid propeller located before the intersection (Inboard Propeller, indicated as IP) between the strut and the wing and N smaller fully electric identical propellers distributed in the part of the wing between the tip and the intersection of the wing and strut (Outboard Propellers, referred to as OB). The LARW airframe is loosely based on a previous LARW airframe developed during the H2020 CleanSky2 project RHEA [15]. The airfoil adopted for the wing is a standard GAW-2 and the airfoil used for the strut is a NACA0024. The wing has a single twist determined by a linear interpolation between the twist at root and the twist at tip. The strut has no twist. The fuselage and fairings have been taken from the literature [14] and the wing-strut junction is fixed at 50% of wing span. The wing area is chosen to be equal to the one of the Airbus A320 aircraft, i.e. 122.4 m², and any changes in the geometry of the wing is constrained to maintain the wing area constant. This implies that any change in the Aspect Ratio of the wing will implicitly determine a change in the span of the wing and strut. Assumptions have been made to address the propellers geometry and operational conditions. Namely it has been assumed that the propellers' Mach at tip is 0.8 and the efficiency of the IP is 80% while the efficiency of the OP is 85%. The total Thrust is assumed to be equal to 1.15 times the maximum Drag observed over the entire parameter space evaluated via a VLM method, i.e. 40,000N (20,000N per wing). The additional 15% is introduced in order to account for contingency needs during flight and additional drag coming from a tail and the propellers. The inboard and outboard (referred to by the subscripts IP and OP) propellers' rpm is computed using the advance ratio, J , definition and the imposition of cruise altitude at 8,000 m and the Mach at the propellers' tip, i.e.

$$J_{IP,OP} = \frac{V_{A,IP,OP}}{n_{IP,OP} D_{IP,OP}} \rightarrow \text{rpm}_{IP,OP} = \frac{M_{TIP} \sqrt{\gamma R T}}{D_{IP,OP}} \cdot 60 \quad (2)$$

where D is the diameter of the propeller and $\sqrt{\gamma R T}$ is the speed of sound at the cruise altitude. A schematic of the aircraft is shown in Figure 1 with two exemplary configuration for the distributed propulsion. The set of parameters for the analysis are split into two groups: one containing the geometrical parameters for the airframe as indicated in Table 1 and referred to by the calligraphic letter \mathcal{G} and a second set referring to the propellers parameters reported in Table 2 and referred to by the calligraphic letter \mathcal{P} . Three different configurations for the DHEP are considered with different number of propellers, namely 4, 6 and 8. The parameter space is therefore a 11-dimensional parameter for each one of the three DHEP configurations. The operating conditions in which the sensitivity study will be made are reported in Table 3. Table 4 reports the changes in geometry and operational conditions resulting from the combination of the assumptions made and the choice of \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{P} .

Fig. 1 LARW-DHEP aircraft concept. 6-propellers DP with 25 AR concept (left), 4-propellers DP with 15 AR concept (right)

The HDMR sensitivity will target the $C_L(\alpha)$ curve for a range of angles of attack between -5° and 10° . These will consider realistic operational incidences excluding the stall conditions. To achieve this goal two distinct scalar functions have been considered, namely the slope of the curve, i.e. $C_{L,\alpha}$, and the intercept a 0 degrees of incidence, i.e. C_{L0} . Under the assumption that within the given range of angles of attack the curve is a straight line,

$$C_L(\alpha) = C_{L0} + C_{L,\alpha} \alpha \quad (3)$$

Two separate HDMR analyses will therefore be made to characterise and quantify the sensitivity each one of the two scalar response functions with respect to the airframe and propellers parameters. The two analyses will be made then three times, one for each choice of the number of propellers, i.e. 4, 6 and 8.

	AR	Taper Ratio	Root twist [°]	Tip twist [°]	Strut inc. [°]	Strut chord [m]	Root t/c	Tip t/c
Min	15	0.22	-3	-5	-3	0.906	0.12	0.09
Max	25	0.42	3	1	3	1.597	0.18	0.14

Table 1 Geometrical parameters for the LARW clean (no DP) airframes, i.e. the set \mathcal{G}

	Diameter of Inboard Propeller (IP) [m]	Diameter of Outboard Propellers (OP) [m]	Thrust _{IP} /Thrust _{tot}
Min	3.8	1.3	0.7
Max	4.8	1.6	0.85

Table 2 Parameters for the distributed propulsion system made of 1 larger hybrid propeller and N (3, 5, and 7) smaller electric propellers, i.e. the set \mathcal{P}

Mach _{cruise}	Altitude [m]	α range [°]	Mach _{TIP}	η_{IP}	η_{OP}	Wing area [m ²]	Strut-wing jct. [% of span]
0.6	8,000	[-5; 10]	0.8	80%	85%	122.4	50

Table 3 Operational parameters and assumptions

	Wing span [m]	Strut span [m]	Wing root chord [m]	Wingtip chord [m]	rpm _{IP}	rpm _{OP}
Min	21.42	10.71	2.59	0.61	3,075	9,225
Max	27.66	13.83	3.54	1.4	3,884	11,354

Table 4 Implicit changes in geometrical and operational parameters for LARW-DHEP aircraft not explicitly considered in the sets \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{P}

Fig. 3 Clean (no-DP) LARW-SBW airframe aerodynamic validation. their minimum value (left), configuration with all geometrical parameters at their maximum value (right)

III. Development and validation of the surrogate for LARW-DHEP $C_L(\alpha)$ curve

The aim to generate knowledge to be used within a conceptual design phase has led to the development of a very fast aerodynamic surrogate for the LARW-DHEP $C_L(\alpha)$ curve so that a large parameter space can be explored more efficiently than with the VLM method. Figure 2 illustrates the concept of the surrogate used in this work. The idea is to develop first a surrogate for the aerodynamics of a clean LARW airframe, i.e. an airframe that does not have any propeller, see first term in the Figure. Subsequently this surrogate is corrected to account for the blowing of the propellers, see second term in the Figure and eventually to combine the two in such a way that given as inputs the set of parameters for the airframe shape and the propellers, the $C_L(\alpha)$ curve can be obtained by means of equation (3). The following sections will illustrate the development of each surrogate and the corresponding validation. In the present work, the validation is made by referring to the VLM solutions obtained respectively for the clean, i.e. no-DP, and the complete, i.e. airframe+DP, aircraft configuration.

Fig. 2 Schema of the generation of the surrogate for LARW-DHEP $C_L(\alpha)$

A. Clean (no DP) airframe aerodynamics

The first surrogate is obtained by making use of the HDMR approach such that the $C_L(\alpha)$ curve of a clean LARW strut-braced wing (SBW) airframe can be computed by means of a formula equivalent to (1), where for a given value of the angle of attack, $\bar{\alpha}$, the Lift coefficient is computed as follows:

$$C'_L(\bar{\alpha}) = \bar{C}'_L(\bar{\alpha}) + C'_L(\bar{\alpha}; \mathcal{G}_1) + C'_L(\bar{\alpha}; \mathcal{G}_2) + \dots + C'_L(\bar{\alpha}; \mathcal{G}_{N_g}) + C'_L(\bar{\alpha}; \mathcal{G}_1, \mathcal{G}_2) + \dots + C'_L(\bar{\alpha}; \mathcal{G}_{1,\dots,11}) \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{C}'_L(\bar{\alpha})$ indicates the Lift coefficient at given $\bar{\alpha}$ with all the \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{P} at the central value in their respective range, \mathcal{G}_1 represents the wing Aspect Ratio, \mathcal{G}_2 represents the wing Taper Ratio and so on. $\mathcal{G}_{1,\dots,11}$ indicates the 11-factor interaction among all the parameters and it is equivalent the last term in equation (1). The decomposition generates the Lift coefficient curve by sweeping through the range of angles of attack in Table 3. The adaptive HDMR procedure is performed by using the VLM to generate an initial Design of Experiments and any subsequent evaluation of the aerodynamics of the clean airframe. Figure 3 illustrates two examples of airframe configurations at the two opposite corners of the 8-th dimensional hypercube. The HDMR expansion for C_L is truncated according to a 1% variance criterion relative to the total variance, under the assumption of uniform input parameter distributions. This is then additionally enriched with data from other adaptive sampling studies for Drag and pitching moment coefficients (not shown or discussed in this study), leading to an overall well-rounded and rich set of samples from which to build the

Fig. 4 Kriging surrogate for HDMR terms. C_L vs Aspect Ratio (left), C_L vs wing root twist (right)

Kriging surrogates. The number of VLM samples used for the surrogates sums to 2,347, 526 of which came directly from adaptively sampling for C_L . Each relevant subdomain, i.e. any subdomain that provides significant changes to the Lift coefficients according to the criterion indicated above, identified by the HDMR decomposition is eventually rendered by an analytical formula using a Universal Kriging metamodel [16]. The Kriging model used has a constant basis universal Kriging $\mu(\mathcal{G}_i)$, with an ordinary Kriging covariance function $C(x, x_i)$, which is a generalised exponential with a correlation length of $1E-3$ and an exponent of $2 - 1E-8$, i.e.

$$C'_L(\bar{\alpha}; \mathcal{G}_i) = \mu(\mathcal{G}_i) + \sum_{j=1}^N \gamma_j C(\mathcal{G}_i, \mathcal{G}_{i,j}) \quad (5)$$

The Kriging covariance coefficients γ_i are then optimised to fit the given sub-domain dataset for minimum mean square error, giving the surrogate that can be used to estimate the ΔC_L for any given parameter values in the sub-domain. Figure 4 shows two examples of the Kriging metamodel respectively for \mathcal{G}_1 and \mathcal{G}_3 , i.e. the Aspect Ratio and the wing root twist. It has to be noted how the different VLM solutions represented by the black circles are characterised by some noise/scattering. This is to be referred to the VLM algorithm used and the refinement of the aircraft surface discretisation. The resulting HDMR-Kriging based surrogate is eventually validated for a number of different geometries and angles of attack to assess the accuracy of the clean-aircraft surrogate. This validation exercise is presented in Figure 5 in the form of comparison of actual C_L values with the VLM solution and in terms of error over the range of angles of attack. The trends illustrate an almost constant error over the incidence with percentage error below 10% for most of the cases.

B. Correction for distributed propellers

Once the clean-aircraft surrogate has been derived, then a correction to account for the presence of distributed propellers is applied. Therefore while the previous step deals only with airframe geometrical parameters in the set \mathcal{G} , this step introduces the propellers parameters in the set \mathcal{P} . The correction step follows the approach originally developed by M. Hepperle at DLR [17]. The correction makes use of the classical momentum theory to account for the accelerated flow in the wake of the propeller disk and further improves the prediction by accounting for the changes in the local angle of attack resulting from the changes in local velocity magnitude. The correction modifies the spanwise distribution of Lift (and Drag) due to the presence of the propellers. The change in the total force for a given α with respect to a clean wing with a given \mathcal{G} , ΔL , is then obtained by integration along the wingspan. The ΔC_L is computed from the ΔL and the dynamic pressure at cruise conditions and eventually applied to the C'_L obtained from the first surrogate. Figure 6 illustrates the intervention of the correction methodology along the wing. In the figure the red shaded areas are those affected by the local changes. For clarity of the image the shaded area is shown only on one configuration but it applies equivalently to all airframes and number of propellers.

The propellers' correction is eventually validated against the VLM method for different geometries of the airframe and different settings for the propellers. The validation is shown in Figure 7 in the same format used for the no-DP

Fig. 5 LARW clean airframe aerodynamic surrogate validation. C_L values for different geometries over a range of angles of attack (left), absolute error in C_L value (right). Case with 4 propellers

Fig. 6 LARW-DHEP correction for propellers (shown in red only for one case). All parameters (\mathcal{G} and \mathcal{P}) at their minimum value (left), configuration with all parameters (\mathcal{G} and \mathcal{P}) at their maximum value (right)

HDMR-Kriging based aerodynamic surrogate. In this case, the discrepancy between the two methods is more pronounced and a positive linear trend is observed over the range of angle of attack but with an error that for most of the cases remains in the 10% area. The validation is shown here only in the case for 4 propellers but the same trend is observed for more propellers.

C. Surrogates for C_L, α and C_{L0}

Once the surrogate for the clean airframe and the one introducing the propellers correction are combined together, it is possible to make define a semi-analytical relation that takes as input \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{P} and by sweeping the range of angles of attack generate the $C_L(\alpha)$ curve by evaluating the Lift coefficients at the different α . The final step in the development of the aerodynamic surrogate is to use a linear fit to the computed points so that the slope $C_{L,\alpha}$ and the intercept C_{L0} can be computed. Figures 8 and 9 show the validation step made for the combined surrogate to be used in the HDMR study for the present work. The Figures report the comparison between the analytical surrogate of the $C_L(\alpha)$ curve obtained by inserting the computed $C_{L,\alpha}$ and C_{L0} into equation (3) and the corresponding VLM solution equipped with actuator disk. The Figure also indicates the set \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{P} by means of spider plots. Overall it is observed that the agreement is satisfactory with moderate changes due to the change in the number of propellers as also illustrated by the errors in slope and intercept in Figure 10.

Fig. 7 LARW-DHEP aerodynamic surrogate validation. C_L values for different geometries over a range of angles of attack (left), absolute error in C_L value (right). Case with 4 propellers

Fig. 8 LARW-DHEP validation of the $C_L; \alpha$ and $C_L; 0$ HDMR surrogates against VLM+actuator disk solution for a few distinct airframe configurations for different distributed propellers. The spider plot represents the given aircraft in the 11-dimensional parameter space

Fig. 9 LARW-DHEP validation of the $C_L; \alpha$ and $C_L; \alpha = 0$ HDMR surrogates against VLM+actuator disk solution for a few distinct airframe configurations for different distributed propellers. The spider plot represents the given aircraft in the 11-dimensional parameter space

Fig. 10 LARW-DHEP aerodynamic surrogate validation. Error on C_L, α (left), error on $C_L, \alpha = 0$ (right) for 10 different LARW-DHEP

IV. Results of the sensitivity study

The results of the sensitivity study are presented in this section considering the three different configuration for the distributed propellers. The analysis will report the sensitivity with respect to the central configuration, i.e. the configuration for which all the \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{P} are taken at the central value of their respective range. While the central point is usually considered to be a design configuration for which a sensitivity study needs to be done, in this case, the perspective is slightly different since the present analysis is to serve a conceptual design stage for which a baseline aircraft is not available. Therefore it is important to note that the focus will be on analysing the overall changes of lifting properties over the given range of parameters rather than exploring in details the gradients at the central point. Table 5 reports the values of $C_{L,\alpha}$ and C_{L0} for all \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{P} at the centre of the 11-dimensional hypercube.

	4 props	6 props	8 props
$C_{L,\alpha}$	0.143 / deg	0.143 / deg	0.142 / deg
C_{L0}	0.128	0.127	0.126

Table 5 Central values for the scalar response functions for different DP configurations

Increment function	Min $\Delta C_{L,\alpha}$	Max $\Delta C_{L,\alpha}$	Range $\Delta C_{L,\alpha}$	Cumulative $\sum \Delta C_{L,\alpha}$
Aspect Ratio	-9.74%	+7.85%	17.59% (0.0252/deg)	-
Strut chord	-1.68%	+2.44%	4.12% (0.00591/deg)	-
Wingtip t/c	-0.39%	+1.76%	2.15% (0.00308/deg)	-
Taper Ratio	-0.61%	+0.65%	1.26% (0.00181/deg)	-
Wingtip twist	-1.05%	+0.17%	1.22% (0.00175/deg)	-
Wing root t/c	-0.02%	+1.18%	1.19% (0.00171/deg)	-
Strut incidence	-0.85%	+0.01%	0.86% (0.00123/deg)	-
Strut chord & Wingtip twist	-0.33%	+1.29%	1.61% (0.00230/deg)	5.04%
Root twist & Strut chord	-0.54%	+1.06%	1.60% (0.00229/deg)	4.59%
Strut incidence & Strut chord	-0.35%	+1.24%	1.59% (0.00228/deg)	5.77%
Strut chord & Wing root t/c	-1.18%	+0.09%	1.27% (0.00182/deg)	4.74%
Taper ratio & Strut chord	-0.64%	+0.13%	0.77% (0.00110/deg)	5.16%

Table 6 Sensitivity table for $C_{L,\alpha}$ reporting the most important increment functions for 4 propellers. The values are % changes with respect to the slope of the central point $\bar{C}_{L,\alpha} = 0.143/\text{deg}$

A. $C_{L,\alpha}$ and C_{L0} for 4 distributed propellers

The results for a DP configuration with 4 propellers are reported in Tables 6 and 7 for the slope and intercept respectively. The tables show all the n-factor interactions from the HDMR decomposition that will induce a change in the two scalar functions that is at least 1% of the central value. The last n-factor interaction reported in the table is a verification of the above criterion. The most important parameter influencing the slope is Aspect Ratio, leading to a change of 17.6% of the central value over the given range of AR. This is somehow expected from the aerodynamic point of view as a larger aspect ratio reduces the downwash the wing is flying in and therefore limiting the backward tilt of the Lift vector due to the finite span wing aerodynamics. Changes in the Aspect Ratio also lead to the largest increase/decrease of the slope among all the other parameters. It is also worth noting that changes in the AR also induce implicit changes in the span of the strut with beneficial effects on the slope. In this respect, it is worth observing that in the present analysis, the reference surface has always been considered the wing surface, therefore any parameter in \mathcal{G} that influences the surface of the strut will be revealed as a sensible one due the chosen normalisation approach. That explains also the prominent role of the strut chord in the sensitivity of the slope in the 1- and 2-factors interactions.

Increment function	Min ΔC_{L0}	Max ΔC_{L0}	Range ΔC_{L0}	Cumulative $\sum \Delta C_{L0}$
Wing root twist	-89.05%	+110.00%	199.05% (0.254)	-
Wingtip twist	-28.61%	+66.77%	95.39% (0.122)	-
Aspect Ratio	-21.95%	+67.02%	88.96% (0.114)	-
Strut incidence	-43.12%	+45.08%	88.20% (0.113)	-
Wingtip t/c	-8.71%	+19.69%	28.40% (0.0363)	-
Wing root t/c	-1.04%	+26.78%	27.82% (0.0356)	-
Strut chord	-11.60%	+14.25%	25.85% (0.0330)	-
Taper ratio	-9.54%	+7.53%	17.07% (0.0218)	-
Outboard prop diameter	-0.18%	+0.22%	0.41% (0.00052)	-

Table 7 Sensitivity table for C_{L0} reporting the most important increment functions for 4 propellers. The values are % changes with respect to the zero intercept of the central point $\bar{C}_{L0} = 0.128$

The sensitivity on the intercept illustrates only the 1-factor terms in the decomposition with all the other n-factors providing a contribution that is smaller than 1% of the central value. What is to be noted in this case is the much larger influence of each parameter on the intercept with the wing root twist inducing a change as high as 199.05% of the central value. From an aerodynamic point of view is to be expected that the wing twist plays the most important role in

the intercept. In both the case of slope and intercept it is noticeable that the propeller parameters have a very minimal influence. Figure 11 illustrate the predominant 1-factor increment function for both slope and intercept together with some verification data (the crosses in the plots) obtained with the VLM method that shows a fair comparison between the surrogate developed in this work and the reference VLM solution used to build the surrogate. Eventually Figure 12 shows the VLM solutions for the points used for verification.

Fig. 11 Most important single factors increment functions for 4 distributed propellers configuration. $C_{L,\alpha}$ (left), C_{L0} (right)

Fig. 12 Pressure Coefficient at $\alpha = 0^\circ$ for the validation of the sensitivity results for 4 propellers via VLM solutions. $AR=21.5$ for $C_{L,\alpha}$ (left), Wing root twist 0.99° for C_{L0} (right). All other parameters at their central value

B. $C_{L,\alpha}$ and C_{L0} for 6 and 8 distributed propellers

The sensitivity results for the configuration with 6 propellers are shown in Tables 8 and 9 while the results for the configuration with 8 propellers are shown in Tables 10 and 11. Also in these cases the trend and considerations made for the case with 4 propellers apply. This refers to the identification of the most important 1-factor increment functions that are respectively Aspect Ratio for the slope and Wing root twist for the intercept and also refers to the relative sensitivity of the two scalars with respect to the geometrical parameters of the airframe, i.e. a much larger variation is observed in the intercept than in the slope. The propellers parameters still do not play a major role in

affecting the lifting properties of the wing. Also for 6 and 8 propellers only the 1-factor increment functions provide an impact larger than 1% on the central values. The cumulative effect of the 2-factors increment functions, i.e. the term $\sum_{i=1}^{N_u} F_i(U_i) + \sum_{i < j \leq N_u} F_{i,j}(U_i, U_j)$ in equation (1) is noted to be higher than in the case of configuration with 4 propellers in the case of the slope sensitivity. This behaviour might be related to the fact that for the given range of \mathcal{G} the presence of 6 or 8 propellers along the wing affects the overall aerodynamics more than the case of 4 propellers. This is somehow to be expected and the outcome of the analysis is to quantify such effect and note that still for the given ranges there are not so many differences in 2-factor interactions between 6 and 8 propellers.

Increment function	Min $\Delta C_{L,\alpha}$	Max $\Delta C_{L,\alpha}$	Range $\Delta C_{L,\alpha}$	Cumulative $\sum \Delta C_{L,\alpha}$
Aspect Ratio	-9.76%	+7.58%	17.34% (0.0248/deg)	-
Strut chord	-1.58%	+3.15%	4.72% (0.00675/deg)	-
Wingtip t/c	-0.25%	+1.85%	2.10% (0.0030/deg)	-
Wing tip twist	-1.64%	+0.14%	1.77% (0.00253/deg)	-
Wing root t/c	-0.03%	+1.21%	1.24% (0.00177/deg)	-
Taper Ratio	-0.41%	+0.65%	1.06% (0.00152/deg)	-
Root twist	-0.07%	+0.76%	0.82% (0.00117/deg)	-
Aspect Ratio & Wing root t/c	-1.57%	+1.48%	3.06% (0.00438/deg)	20.20%
Strut chord & Wing root t/c	-2.44%	+0.20%	2.64% (0.00378/deg)	5.08%
Wing root twist & Strut chord	-1.34%	+1.20%	2.54% (0.00363/deg)	6.25%
Aspect Ratio & Strut incidence	-0.24%	+1.53%	1.77% (0.00253/deg)	18.85%
Aspect Ratio & Wing root twist	-1.39%	+0.04%	1.43% (0.00206/deg)	18.41%
Aspect Ratio & Strut chord	-1.39%	+0.02%	1.41% (0.00202/deg)	22.17%
Strut chord & Wingtip t/c	-0.98%	+0.03%	1.01% (0.00144/deg)	6.32%
Strut incidence & Strut chord	-0.71%	+0.27%	0.98% (0.00140/deg)	5.62%

Table 8 Sensitivity table for $C_{L,\alpha}$ reporting the most important increment functions for 6 propellers. The values are % changes with respect to the slope of the central point $\bar{C}_{L,\alpha} = 0.143/\text{deg}$

Increment function	Min ΔC_{L0}	Max ΔC_{L0}	Range ΔC_{L0}	Cumulative $\sum \Delta C_{L0}$
Wing root twist	-89.91%	+109.50%	199.40% (0.253)	-
Wingtip twist	-28.40%	+65.91%	94.31% (0.119)	-
Strut incidence	-42.74%	+47.14%	89.88% (0.114)	-
Aspect Ratio	-21.95%	+67.66%	89.62% (0.0348)	-
Wingtip t/c	-7.25%	+20.23%	27.48% (0.0339)	-
Wing root t/c	-1.40%	+25.40%	26.80% (0.0294)	-
Strut chord	-8.44%	+14.76%	23.21% (0.0214)	-
Taper ratio	-9.93%	+7.00%	16.92% (0.00049)	-
Inboard prop diameter	-0.17%	+0.22%	0.39% (0.00030)	-

Table 9 Sensitivity table for C_{L0} reporting the most important increment functions for 6 propellers. The values are % changes with respect to the zero intercept of the central point $\bar{C}_{L0} = 0.127$

Figures 13 and 15 show the 1-factor increment function for the most relevant parameters for the slope and intercept for 6 and 8 propellers respectively. The overall trend is rather linear and the verification with the VLM solution shows again a fair agreement. The Pressure coefficients for the VLM solutions for 6 and 8 propellers are shown in Figures 14 and 16.

Fig. 13 Most important single factors increment functions for 6 distributed propellers configuration. $C_{L,\alpha}$ (left), C_{L0} (right)

Fig. 14 Pressure Coefficient at $\alpha = 0^\circ$ for the validation of the sensitivity results for 6 propellers via VLM solutions. $AR=21.5$ for $C_{L,\alpha}$ (left), Wing root twist 0.99° for C_{L0} (right). All other parameters at their central value

Increment function	Min $\Delta C_{L,\alpha}$	Max $\Delta C_{L,\alpha}$	Range $\Delta C_{L,\alpha}$	Cumulative $\sum \Delta C_{L,\alpha}$
Aspect Ratio	-9.83%	+7.43%	17.26% (0.0245/deg)	-
Strut chord	-1.58%	+3.33%	4.91% (0.00698/deg)	-
Wingtip t/c	-0.24%	+1.86%	2.09% (0.00297/deg)	-
Wingtip twist	-1.27%	+0.11%	1.38% (0.00196/deg)	-
Wing root t/c	-0.03%	+1.21%	1.24% (0.00176/deg)	-
Taper Ratio	-0.39%	+0.64%	1.03% (0.00146/deg)	-
Wing root twist	-0.06%	+0.72%	0.79% (0.00112/deg)	-
Wing root twist & Strut chord	-1.46%	+1.44%	2.90% (0.00412/deg)	6.71%
Aspect Ratio & Wing root t/c	-0.62%	+2.24%	2.86% (0.00406/deg)	21.04%
Strut chord & Wing root t/c	-2.66%	+0.09%	2.75% (0.00391/deg)	5.08%
Strut chord & Aspect Ratio	-1.63%	+0.27%	1.91% (0.00271/deg)	22.01%
Strut incidence & Strut chord	-1.00%	+0.91%	1.90% (0.00269/deg)	5.81%
Strut incidence & Aspect Ratio	-0.12%	+1.35%	1.47% (0.00209/deg)	18.82%
Strut chord & Wingtip t/c	-1.21%	+0.01%	1.22% (0.00173/deg)	6.23%
Aspect Ratio & Wing root twist	-1.08%	+0.04%	1.13% (0.00161/deg)	18.48%
Aspect Ratio & Wingtip t/c	-0.21%	+0.33%	0.54% (0.000767/deg)	19.87%

Table 10 Sensitivity table for $C_{L,\alpha}$ reporting the most important increment functions for 8 propellers. The values are % changes with respect to the slope of the central point $\bar{C}_{L,\alpha} = 0.142/\text{deg}$

Increment function	Min ΔC_{L0}	Max ΔC_{L0}	Range ΔC_{L0}	Cumulative $\sum \Delta C_{L0}$
Wing root twist	-89.62%	+108.90%	198.50% (0.250)	-
Wingtip twist	-29.88%	+65.11%	94.99% (0.119)	-
Strut incidence	-42.88%	+47.75%	90.63% (0.114)	-
Aspect Ratio	-21.49%	+67.59%	89.09% (0.112)	-
Wingtip t/c	-7.27%	+20.44%	27.71% (0.0349)	-
Wing root t/c	-1.31%	+26.12%	27.43% (0.0345)	-
Strut chord	-8.25%	+14.14%	22.39% (0.0281)	-
Taper ratio	-9.95%	+6.93%	16.89% (0.0212)	-
Inboard prop diameter	-0.19%	+0.25%	0.45% (0.00057)	-

Table 11 Sensitivity table for C_{L0} reporting the most important increment functions for 8 propellers. The values are % changes with respect to the zero intercept of the central point $\bar{C}_{L0} = 0.126$

Fig. 15 Most important single factors increment functions for 8 distributed propellers configuration. $C_{L,\alpha}$ (left), C_{L0} (right)

Fig. 16 Pressure Coefficient at $\alpha = 0^\circ$ for the validation of the sensitivity results for 8 propellers via VLM solutions. $AR=21.5$ for $C_{L,\alpha}$ (left), Wing root twist 0.99° for C_{L0} (right). All other parameters at their central value

V. Final remarks and outlook

Performing extensive parametric and sensitivity studies for the next-generation of non-conventional aircraft is a key step towards achieving the sustainable aviation goals. The key findings reported in the present work refer to the introduction of an approach to the generation of a fast surrogate for the prediction of the lifting performance of a LARW-DHEP airframe using a strut brace wing and its use in the sensitivity study of such a non-conventional configuration in support of conceptual design stages. The sensitivity study has identified the most important geometrical parameters for different DP configurations suggesting that the parameters of the propellers induce an effect that is second order with respect to other key plan form shape parameters such as the Aspect Ratio. The analysis has also revealed that, for the given ranges of parameters, there is a much larger sensitivity of the $C_L(\alpha)$ curve intercept than its slope. The progression of the present work is to complete the aerodynamic analysis to include Drag and Moment coefficients.

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